

www.bjisrd.com

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ART OF GIVING IN UZBEKISTAN

U.Kudratova

Associate professor of Tashkent State University of Economics, Uzbekistan

Abstract: In creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, we directly rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries and the rich spiritual heritage of our ancestors. Today, the development of national folklore, music and folk performance art is in danger of disappearing. Because the increase of threats in the form of "mass culture" in society, familiarity of young people with western culture, neglect of national culture in some cases creates disdain. In order to protect ourselves from such a danger, the development of the spiritual and cultural level of our youth, the development of national status, the epics of giving, folk tunes and songs, and the art of dance and Askiya is one of the important issues of state policy.

Keywords: Renaissance, epics, spiritual and cultural level, national folklore.

Introduction

As the head of our state, Sh. Mirziyoev, noted: "Spirituality in society must be one step ahead of other areas, spirituality must become a new force, a new movement!"¹

At the extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment of the Republic held on December 22, 2023 under the chairmanship of the President, it was decided to further develop the art of status and giving, along with all branches of the cultural sphere, the existing performing and creative schools, and in this regard a special emphasis was placed on the issue of further strengthening the research and rehabilitation of mothers on a scientific basis, specific assignments and tasks were defined in this regard.

The conference chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the proposals and initiatives presented at it, and the current tasks set are evidence of the beginning of a new era in the development of our national status and art of giving. While the position of experts in this field is highly valued, it also imposes great responsibility and tasks on them.

It is worth noting that a special fund for the support of spirituality and creativity and an institute of socio-spiritual research were established in our country. For this reason, 45 billion soums are allocated annually to support spirituality and creativity.

In order to preserve and enrich our national traditions, Maqom, Bakhshichilik and Askiya art centers were established. Also, more than 20 institutions, such as the "Bahor" dance ensemble, the State Philharmonic, and the State Symphony Orchestra, were launched.

The volume of state support for culture and art increased 5 times compared to 2017, and more than 12 billion soums were allocated for these purposes in 2023.

¹ It is a period of new reforms in our spiritual life. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment on December 22. December 23, 2023 No. 274 (8617)

Materials and methods

A special system has been created to promote our rich and unique cultural heritage to the world. Such international festivals as "Maqom", "Bakhshichilik", "Hunarmandchilik", "Lazgi", which are regularly held in our country, serve this purpose.

Currently, "Uzbek culture days" were held at a high level in 24 foreign countries, including neighboring countries. It is clear to all of us that the unique examples of our national culture presented in countries such as France, Germany, China, and Saudi Arabia surprised the world public and they rediscovered Uzbekistan for themselves.

In the future, such exhibitions are planned to be held in Italy, Great Britain, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates.

Bakhshchilik is a childhood song of humanity. For this reason, in order to preserve the historical heritage and pass it on to the next generation, our president Sh.Mirziyoev at the International Bakhshi festival "*...we will present folk art, known in different countries as bakhshi, jiro, aqin, manaschi, poet, oshiq*, our own it is necessary to fully support the rare talent of people who embody the skills of poetry, music, and singing.

On the initiative of the head of our state, on April 25, 2018, "On measures for the further development and improvement of philanthropy and folklore", on November 1, 2018, "On holding the international festival of the art of philanthropy", 2019 On May 14, 2019, the decision "On measures to further develop the art of philanthropy" and on April 6, 2019, in his speech at the opening ceremony of the International Festival of philanthropy and other normative legal documents on the development of this field tasks are defined.

By the 20th century, the art of bakhshiki and khalfalik, as well as epic writing, is completely fading in many regions of the world, and even in some regions of our republic, it is experiencing the process of fading.

Literature review

V.M. Zhirmunsky, H.T.Zaripov, M.S.Saidov, T.M.Mirzaev, S.R.Rozimboev, about bakhshi, khalfa, performance and performance in Uzbek folklore studies, bakhshi skill and performance of khalfa in general, their artistic and aesthetic nature and specific aspects. Scientists such as H. J. Abdullaev, M. Joraev, Sh. Turdimov, J. Eshonkul, N. A. Rahmonov, O. Madaev expressed important opinions and published monographic studies².

However, a number of issues, such as Bakhshi, Khalfa, their first sources, gradual development, performance skills, epic schools, storytelling and its influence on oral performance, performer's repertoire, and their unique singing manner, are waiting for their research.

Bakhshi is a creator and at the same time a keeper of epic traditions and passing them on to future generations. The people greatly respect the art of Bakhshiki. That is why the saying "Bakhshili village is brave, Mullah village is coward" is widespread. The power of memory and memory of Bakhsh

sha was deified. The great Uzbek writer, academician Musa Tashmuhammad, son of Oibek Bakhshi, writes: "Before the emergence of a developed written literature, the peoples of Central Asia wrote rich and colorful folklore works in their native language, created songs, fairy tales and epics.

At weddings, parties, holidays and moving to new destinations, the pleasant voice of folk singers-bakhshis, the tunes of *kobiz and drums* sounded. Bakhshis sang in a high spirit about the hard work of ordinary workers, the history of tribes and clans, and the great heroism of their ancestors. Heroic epics form the basis of oral folk literature. Epics, which are a great monument of folk art, express the incomparable feats of the great heroes of their people through monumental images. The heroes of the epic

² Sabirova N. Khorezm Bakhsh and traditions of khalfaliki / MonografiY. - Tashkent: Science, 2021. - 250 p.

are noble people who carry the people's ideas about truth and justice. Folk art is a great wealth of wisdom"³.

Among the Uzbek people, epic singers are called "bakhshi" and there are various variants of this term. The meaning of "bakhshi" is also understood on the basis of terms such as "poet", "jirov", "aqin", "sannovchi", "akhun", "soqi", "jirchi", "composer", which are spread in different regions of the republic. In addition, the most famous bakhshis are called "chechan", "juyruk", "bulbul" out of respect among the people. But in recent years, the term "bakhshi" has been strengthened as the main name. In Khorezm, such bakhshis are called goyanda. There are different interpretations of the term "bakhshi". At the time when Alisher Navoi lived, this term was used in the sense of secretary and mirza⁴.

Bakhshi is an artist, folk storyteller, who sings and recites songs and epics by heart, passing them down from generation to generation. His sweet voice, the melody emanating from his drum, involuntarily excites and excites a person's heart. Bakhshi must know the life and culture of the people, the history of the country he lives in, and must have mastered the art of playing music. Shoberdi Boltaev, Abdunazar Poyonov, Boborayim Mamatmurodov, Karabakhshi Umirov, Abdukahhor and Abdumurot Rahimov, Shomurod Togaev, Ziyodulla Islamov, Norbek bakhshi Abdullaev, Qalandar bakhshi Normetov made a worthy contribution to the development of bakhshi art with their unique performances. they are In the Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Samarkand, Khorezm regions of our republic and the regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the art of bakhshi is developed, and now there are Bulung'ur, Kurgan, Shahrisabz, Kamay, Sherabad, South Tajikistan, Khorezm and Karakalpak epic schools. there is. They differ from each other in their performance methods and repertoire. In particular, the Bulung'ur school of epics has performed heroic epics. In the Kurgon epic school, which is connected with the poets Ergash Jumanbulbul oglu and Polkan, mainly love epics are sung. Representatives of Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Samarkand Bakhshi schools perform songs in a muffled, closed voice, accompanied by drums, and describe the epic process in an open voice.

Main part

In the performance of representatives of the Khorezm school of epics, mainly music leads and texts are memorized. In almost all regions of Uzbekistan, individual performance dominates in the creation of epic works, but in Khorezm, collective performance is the leader. Khorezm epic is distinguished by its ancient roots, unique style and dialect, bright and attractive melodies⁵.

Certain works are being carried out in our country to preserve and develop this unique art created by the high artistic genius of our people. In this regard, the thousandth anniversary of the epic "Alpomish" was widely celebrated in our country, in the city of Termiz, in honor of this great artistic monument, in the city of Samarkand, memorial complexes dedicated to the memory of our famous bakhshis were built, and the honorary title of "People's bakhshi of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was established by our state. should be noted.

Today, there is a folkloric school in the city of Termiz, folklore classes in children's music and art schools in our republic. In our country, many collections of "Folklore of Karakalpak" have been published, and a complex of 100 volumes "Monuments of Uzbek Folk Art" is being published. Recording of the works performed by Bakhshi-poets and their scientific study are ongoing.

The "International Festival of Giving Art", which was held for the first time in Termiz, was widely recognized as a major international cultural event. This festival is scheduled to be held once every 2 years⁶.

³ Oybek. A perfect collection of works. Volume XIX. - Tashkent: Science, 1982. - P. 152 (310).

⁴ Explanatory dictionary of the language of Alisher Navoi's works. - Tashkent: Science, 1983. - P.231.

⁵ Sabirova N. Khorezm Bakhshi and Khalafalik Ananalari / Monograph. - Tashkent: Science, 2021. - 250 p.

⁶ <https://data.egov.uz/uzbKr/data/6107e56d2a2e256d868e872a>

In fact, in the present era of globalization, in the conditions where the negative influence of "mass culture", show business, which has become a commercial tool, attention and interest in folklore art is waning, it is forgotten in many places and needs protection and protection. is being observed. Preventing this, so far in our republic 120 status, philanthropy epics. Folk tunes and songs were recorded in the "Golden Fund"⁷.

In order to further develop the art of giving, which is a vital part of the culture of our people, to increase its place and importance in our national culture and art, to educate the young generation in the spirit of national identity, loyalty to the Motherland, and respect for the historical heritage:

The Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Academy of Sciences, the Union of Writers and the Surkhondarya Regional Government have established the Republican Bakhshi Art Center and the Bakhshi Art Development Fund, which has the status of a legal entity, in the form of a state institution in Termiz.

The following are defined as the main tasks of the Center of the Republic of Bakhshilik Art:

- in-depth study and strengthening of the scientific-theoretical and practical foundations of the art of giving;
- revival and development of unique performance styles of creative schools formed in the field, "master-disciple" traditions;
- supporting the creative and scientific activities of poets, folklorists, teachers and specialists;
- organization of charity art clubs at cultural centers, children's music and art schools and other educational institutions;
- opening a wide path to the creativity of Bakhsh poets, ensuring their active participation in public holidays and cultural events;
- effective use of information and communication technologies, television and Internet opportunities to collect and create a fund of the best examples of the art of bakhshi, to increase their audio and video versions, to widely promote this industry in our country and in the world;
- to strengthen international cooperation in the field of performing arts, to establish a mutual exchange of experience in this regard, including the organization of various international conferences and competitions, concerts and master classes⁸.

The main tasks of the "Development of the Art of Donation" Fund are as follows:

- to support the further development of the art of philanthropy based on the implementation of complex measures in financial and organizational directions;
- providing comprehensive support to bakhshi-poets, poets and jirovs(mean art) operating in our country;
- To provide the institutions of the Ministry of Culture with the necessary literature, training manuals and periodicals related to the art of art;
- strengthening the material and technical base of the charity clubs under the institutions of culture and art, providing them with the necessary instruments and equipment;
- financing of scientific researches, publishing works and complex scientific expeditions related to the art of art;

⁷ It is a period of new reforms in our spiritual life. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment on December 22. December 23, 2023 No. 274 (8617)

⁸ <https://lex.uz/docs/4380951>

- development of patronage of the art of philanthropy, attraction of foreign investments and grants in the field;
- provides for the accumulation of funds from the sources specified in the legislation, ensuring their targeted and effective use⁹.

In 2018, with the initiative of the head of our country, in order to discover talented young people, to familiarize the growing young generation with the rich treasure of folk art, and to support them in every way, in 2018 "Bakhshilar School" was opened in Termiz, "Opera" in Nukus and a school specializing in the art of philanthropy was established. Status schools are also operating in different regions of our republic. For example, our art-loving children grow up in Bukhara Maqom Boarding School specialized in Bukhara Maqom art named after Abdurauf Fitrat, "Maqom School" and "Askiya Schools" established under the Fergana Regional Branch of the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan.

In the decision on the protection, scientific study and promotion of intangible cultural heritage adopted by the initiative of the President:

- Establishment of the Institute of Cultural Studies and Intangible Cultural Heritage;
- Allocation of 28 targeted grants for scientific research of "Alpomish", "Gorogli" epics and musical works of Fergana, Tashkent, Khorezm, Bukhara regions;
- transferring more than 3,000 epics, status and folklore works stored in our country's funds into a modern format;
- It was decided to create schools that continue the traditions of 12 unique cultural heritage examples, such as maqam, big singing, bakshiki, satin and adras, pottery and jewelry¹⁰.

Conclusion

We can say that our President Sh.M. We are sure that Mirziyoyev will mobilize all his strength and capabilities to fulfill these tasks assigned to the immortal examples of our national heritage, including the representatives of status and the art of betting. These festivals are organized in order to further develop the national status, the art of epic poetry and the art of giving, to strengthen the feeling of respect and love for these arts in the hearts of the young generation, to further strengthen the creative cooperation, friendship and brotherhood between different peoples. Meetings, scientific researches are a great opportunity to glorify this unique art of ours to the world, an example of incomparable care.

References:

1. It is a period of new reforms in our spiritual life. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment on December 22. December 23, 2023 No. 274 (8617)
2. Sabirova N. Khorezm Bakhsh and traditions of khalfaliki / MonografiY. - Tashkent: Science, 2021. - 250 p.
3. Oybek. A perfect collection of works. Volume XIX. - Tashkent: Science, 1982. - P. 152 (310).
4. Explanatory dictionary of the language of Alisher Navoi's works. - Tashkent: Science, 1983. - P.231.
5. Sabirova N. Khorezm Bakhshi and Khalafalik Ananalari / Monograph. - Tashkent: Science, 2021. - 250 p

⁹ <https://lex.uz/docs/4380951>

¹⁰It is a period of new reforms in our spiritual life. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the extended meeting of the Council of Spirituality and Enlightenment on December 22. December 23, 2023 No. 274 (8617)